

Studies on Some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complex. Part XV. Composition of the Reaction Products of Chromous Chloride and Potassium Ferricyanide

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Conductometric (direct) and potentiometric titrations (direct and reverse) between chromous chloride and potassium ferricyanide indicate the formation of complexes having the composition $\text{KCr}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$ and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$. These results find confirmation on the basis of chemical analysis also. The role of $\text{Cr}^{2+} + \text{FeCy}_6^{3-}$ and $\text{Cr}^{3+} + \text{FeCy}_6^{4-}$ couple on the formation of these complexes has been discussed.

Amongst the metal-ferrocyanogen complexes¹⁻⁵, the chromium complexes offer a new field of study. In a recent communication, Malik⁶ drew attention to the influence of redox potential on the formation of Cu(I), Ti(III and IV), Mn(III), and Cr(II) ferro- and ferricyanides. The present communication is an extension of the earlier studies and deals with the results on the potentiometric and conductometric titrations between chromous chloride and potassium ferricyanide and the chemical analysis of the dried complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chromous chloride crystals, prepared according to Balthis and Bailer⁷⁻⁸, were dissolved in double distilled water and the solution was stored in the storage flask designed by Lingane and Pecsok⁹. The strength of the solution was determined by Rienacker's method¹⁰⁻¹¹ as modified by Lingane⁹. Potassium ferricyanide solution was prepared by dissolving the recrystallised sample in double distilled water and its strength determined iodometrically¹².

Measurements of conductance were carried out by a Cambridge Conductivity Bridge (No. L: 350140) using a four-necked, Jacket type conductivity cell. Potentiometric titra-

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tions were carried out by means of a Pye precision vernier potentiometer (Cat. No. 7508). A platinum wire electrode served as the indicator electrode and S. C. E. as the reference electrode. An air-tight, rubber-corked cell was used for the titrations. Purified nitrogen was used to stir as well as to maintain an inert atmosphere in the cell.

Both direct and reverse (K_3FeCy_6 in the cell and *vice versa*) titrations were carried out at different concentrations of the reagents in both aqueous and aqueous ethanolic media (0.05M, 0.025M, and 0.0125M- K_3FeCy_6 against 0.116M- $CrCl_2$ for direct titrations and 0.05M, 0.025M, and 0.0125M- $CrCl_2$ against 0.1M- K_3FeCy_6 in the case of reverse titrations). Direct conductometric and potentiometric titrations provided ratio $FeCy_6: Cr^{2+}$ as 1:1, whereas the reverse potentiometric titrations indicated the ratio as 1:2. Typical titration curves (direct) are shown in Fig. 1. Reverse conductometric titrations did not provide satisfactory results under the existing conditions.

FIG. 1. Conductometric titration curves.

- Curve 1: 20.0 ml of 0.05M- K_3FeCy_6 against 0.116M- $CrCl_2$ in aq. medium.
 Curve 2: 20.0 0.05M- K_3FeCy_6 against 0.116M- $CrCl_2$ in 20% EtOH.
 Curve 3: 20.0 0.025M- $CrCl_2$ against 0.1M- K_3FeCy_6 in aq. medium.
 Curve 4: 20.0 0.025M- $CrCl_2$ against 0.1M- K_3FeCy_6 in 20% EtOH.
 Curves 3 & 4 (Scale 1 cm = 1 ml.)
 Curves 1 & 2 (Scale 1 cm = 2 ml.)

Analysis of the Complex.—The complexes in the freshly precipitated states were obtained by mixing K_3FeCy_6 (0.116M) and $CrCl_2$ (0.116M) in the molar ratios 1:1 and 1:2 respectively. These were washed several times with air-free distilled water and finally with ether. The water content was determined by heating a weighed amount of the complex in an electric oven at 110°. No loss in weight was observed, indicating formation of the anhydrous complex.

The complex was decomposed by alkali fusion in a platinum dish with NaOH and Na_2O_2 . Iron was converted into the oxide and chromium to sodium chromate. The fused mass was cooled, extracted with hot water, and filtered. The residue consisting of ferric oxide was dissolved in HCl (dil.), reprecipitated with NH_4OH (dil.), filtered, dried, and weighed as Fe_2O_3 in a silica crucible after ignition. Chromium was estimated as chromate iodometrically. Potassium in the extract was estimated as $K_2NaCo(NO_2)_6 \cdot H_2O$.

A combination of Kjeldal's¹³ and Colman's method¹⁴, used by Smith and Griswold¹⁶ (with slight modifications), was employed for the estimation of nitrogen. The results of analysis are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

%Constituent.	Equiv.	Ratio.	%Constituent.	Equiv.	Ratio.
A. 1:1 Complex: $KCr^{III}Fe^{III}Cy_6$ or $KCr^{III}Fe^{II}Cy_6$.			B. 1:2 Complex: $K_2Cr^{III}Fe^{II}Cy_6$.		
K : 10.89	0.2785	1.0	K : 22.74	0.5832	2.00
Cr : 19.56	0.3765	1.3	Cr : 15.08	0.2900	1.00
Fe : 19.04	0.3409	1.2	Fe : 16.25	0.2941	1.01
CN: 42.20	1.6153	5.6	CN: 45.24	1.7472	6.02

DISCUSSION

The system under discussion is different from other metal-ferrocyanogen systems in one particular aspect, viz., the influence of redox potential on the reaction product. In view of the large value of K (2.5×10^{14} , as calculated from the oxidation potential values of the systems:

for the system:

it may be expected that all the ferricyanide ions are reduced to ferrocyanide ions and likewise the chromous ions are oxidised to chromic. The different methods employed in investigating the reaction do not fully support this view point.

Firstly, when potassium ferrocyanide and chromic chloride are the products of the reaction, there should exist the least possibility of their reaction giving rise to a precipitated complex (earlier studies have shown that the two react very slowly at the room temperature, providing a reddish brown soluble complex).

The combining ratio of 2:1 ($Cr^{2+}:FeCy_6^{3-}$), obtained in the reverse potentiometric titrations, provides evidence for the probable formation of chromous ferrocyanide. The reaction appears to take place in two stages:

followed by

The overall reaction being

The complex has the composition $K_2Cr^{II}Fe^{II}Cy_6$.

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14. *Analyst*, 1908, 33, 261.

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The redox influences do not seem to be operative when titrations are carried out in the direct order, i.e., with potassium ferricyanide in the cell. The combining ratio of 1:1, obtained here, signifies that the reduction of potassium ferricyanide by chromous ions is a much slower process than the oxidation of chromous chloride by potassium ferricyanide (as evident from the reverse titration) with the result that the chromous ions react preferably with potassium ferricyanide to afford chromous ferricyanide according to the stoichiometric equation:

to that for the reduction of ferricyanide. Chemical analysis of the 1:1 complex fully supports existence of $\text{KCr}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$. An indication of existence of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$ is also available for the 2:1 complex.

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